

ARRIVE Essential 10: Author Checklist

Study design

For each experiment, provide brief details of study design including:

- a. The groups being compared, including control groups. If no control group has been used, the rationale should be stated.
- b. The experimental unit (e.g. a single animal, litter, or cage of animals).

All experiments compared wild type (Npc1+/+) and mutant (Npc1-/-) mice within the same experiment. Animals were allocated according to genotype and were sex and age matched. Where possible animals of both genotypes were co-housed.

The experimental unit is single animal and is stated in the results for each experiment.

Sample size 2

- c. Specify the exact number of experimental units allocated to each group, and the total number in each experiment. Also indicate the total number of animals used.
- d. Explain how the sample size was decided. Provide details of any *a priori* sample size calculation, if done.

The number of experimental units is stated in the results section for each separate investigation.

Sample size was determined according to previous experience and our previously published studies that have generated statistically significant data sets.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

- e. Describe any criteria used for including and excluding animals (or experimental units) during the experiment, and data points during the analysis. Specify if these criteria were established *a priori*. If no criteria were set, state this explicitly.
- f. For each experimental group, report any animals, experimental units or data points not included in the analysis and explain why. If there were no exclusions, state so.
- g. For each analysis, report the exact value of *n* in each experimental group.

All animals were generated from in house breeding colonies. Animals were genotyped and then allocated based upon sex and equivalent age. Animals of

both genotypes were co-housed.

All animals within experimental groups were analyzed and non were excluded.

The number of animals analyzed is stated for each investigation.

Randomisation 4

h. State whether randomisation was used to allocate experimental units to control and treatment groups. If done, provide the method used to generate the randomisation sequence.

i. Describe the strategy used to minimise potential confounders such as the order of treatments and measurements, or animal/cage location. If confounders were not controlled, state this explicitly.

Animals were allocated based upon genotype and sex, but were otherwise selected without bias. Animals of both genotypes were co-house. Order of any treatments of individual animals within cohorts was randomized.

Blinding

Describe who was aware of the group allocation at the different stages of the experiment (during the allocation, the conduct of the experiment, the outcome assessment, and the data analysis).

Animals were allocated by an individual distinct from the experimenter. Because mutant mice display visible phenotypes at later ages it was not possible to blind the investigator to the genotypes.

Outcome measures

Clearly define all outcome measures assessed (e.g. cell death, molecular markers, or behavioural changes).

Provide species-appropriate details of the animals used, including species, strain and substrain, sex, age or developmental stage, and, if relevant, weight.

For hypothesis-testing studies, specify the primary outcome measure, i.e. the outcome measure that was used to determine the sample size.

The parameter recorded and analyzed for each investigation is stated in the results section for each study.

Statistical methods

Provide details of the statistical methods used for each analysis, including software used.

Describe any methods used to assess whether the data met the assumptions of the

statistical approach, and what was done if the assumptions were not met.

The statistical method used for analysis of data from each study is stated in the legend of each figure. A summary of the statistics for each study is included, together with the level of significance.

Experimental animals

Details of the specific mouse strains, their provenance, details of husbandry are provided in Materials and Methods section.

Experimental procedures

Details of all procedures are provided in Materials and Methods sections. In every case animals were only sampled and did not undergo any additional treatments and experimental and control groups were based upon genotypes.

Results

For each experiment conducted, including independent replications, report:

Summary/descriptive statistics for each experimental group, with a measure of variability where applicable (e.g. mean and SD, or median and range).

If applicable, the effect size with a confidence interval.

The statistical summary, including significance value is provided for each study and is included in the legend of the figure.